

ALL IN TOOLKIT

A Guide to Implementing Inclusive Language

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ABOUT UNITE

EMPLOYING INCLUSIVE LANGUAGE

APPROACHES AND COMPLEXITIES

Language is powerful. It affects individual wellbeing and social dynamics, with the potential to perpetuate or contest prejudice and systemic inequalities. The language that we use, and are exposed to, influences the ways that we think, feel, and behave towards other people. A [2023 study](#) on the impact of hate speech on neurocognitive mechanisms underlying empathy found that exposure to hate speech, communication that attacks or discriminates against people based on characteristics like race, religion, or sexuality, diminishes the brain's ability to understand others' pain, regardless of social group membership (1). Meanwhile, [other research](#) has shown that the use of gender-neutral language is associated with more broadly inclusive and tolerant views, particularly around gender equality and LGBTQIA+ individuals (2).

“Language is also a place of struggle. The oppressed struggle in language to recover ourselves, to reconcile, to reunite, to renew. Our words are not without meaning, they are an action, a resistance.”

- bell hooks, American author, theorist, and educator (3)

For teaching and learning contexts, where staff and students often have diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds, as well as for international projects involving cross-cultural and interdisciplinary teams, developing shared resources to guide language use across activities and outputs can be highly beneficial. Coming to the Erasmus+ project, UNITE, which focuses on inclusion in education, the University College Dublin team knew it was particularly vital that the consortium adopted an active, collaborative approach to language that recognises the impact of expression and the complex systems of power and oppression in which all people, and all languages, are embedded. With our team's guidance, from the outset of the UNITE project, the partners committed to using terminology that not only resists racist, sexist, classist, ableist, LGBTQIA+-phobic, and other discriminatory or harmful language, but works to acknowledge and honour the diversity of identity, culture, and lived experience.

Our approach to language acknowledges the legacies of colonialism within systems of knowledge. These legacies continue to uphold enduring and oppressive racial, cultural, epistemic, and economic hierarchies that were established through the European colonial project. At the same time, it is important to understand how language itself can function as a colonial tool. Historically, European languages have been violently imposed upon colonised peoples, displacing and erasing Indigenous languages and, by extension, cultural practices and worldviews. To this day, colonial languages are often positioned as superior, suppressing the languages and ethnolects of historically marginalised peoples and reinforcing existing racial, cultural, and class hierarchies. When discussing inclusive language strategies, it is vital to recognise that, even while aiming to respect particular experiences and communities, one may inadvertently prescribe cultural ideals or practices that minoritise or erase the cultures, histories, and experiences of others (4).

Terms relating to culture, race, gender, sexuality, disability, neurodiversity, and other dimensions of identity, community, and experiences of oppression are inherently multifaceted and nuanced. These terms evolve over time and are influenced by regionally and culturally specific factors, such as language conventions, social norms, and dominant practices and understandings. For instance, many languages use grammatical gender, which can influence how people conceptualise and discuss gender identity and social roles, and may affect how terms related to gender, sexuality, or inclusion are translated and understood. Therefore, incorporating non-binary language or non-gendered terms into languages that traditionally use grammatical gender involves careful consideration and the adoption of linguistic strategies, such as neutral pronouns, inclusive suffixes, or restructured phrasing, in order to ensure clarity, cultural resonance, and respect for gender diversity. As another example, while inclusive language guides often recommend a person-first approach over an identity-first one (e.g., “person with a disability” vs. “a disabled person”) to highlight individual personhood, many [disability activists contest this](#). They argue it can portray disability negatively, diminish pride and community, and obscure the impact of systemic ableism in producing societal barriers (5). The choice between person-first and identity-first language is therefore complex and context-dependent, and should aim to respect the preferences of those being referred to.

DEVELOPING AN INCLUSIVE LANGUAGE RESOURCE

INSIGHTS AND STRATEGIES

In consideration of these social, cultural, and linguistic complexities, we collaboratively strategised to develop and streamline the language used across the project's different work packages. The goals were to:

- 1** Ensure that language utilised across project activities is respectful, community-endorsed, non-stereotypical, and non-discriminatory.

- 2** Enhance accessibility of project outputs through clear, consistent, and understandable terminology.

- 3** Align with best practices emerging from academic and activist movements and existing guides and resources, such as the American Psychological Association's [Inclusive Language Guide](#) (6).

- 4** Create a space for critical discussion and ongoing development of project language, rather than a static and exhaustive list of terms.

Producing a coherent, widely applicable language guide within an international, multilingual, and interdisciplinary project presents many complexities. Terminology varies by cultural context, and language describing race, gender, disability, and related topics is continually evolving. In translation, some terms may be viewed as outdated, offensive, or unclear in certain cultural or linguistic contexts, while the same terms may be widely accepted elsewhere. Although English is the primary language of UNITE under the Erasmus+ programme, partners in different countries use other languages (Czech, Dutch, Italian, Portuguese, Spanish) for project descriptions and output dissemination. A cross-project glossary of terms thus was developed not only to provide a guide for producing project materials in the English language, but also to verify translations for clarity and cultural appropriateness.

GUIDELINES FOR CREATING AN INCLUSIVE LANGUAGE RESOURCE

Using the process of developing UNITE’s glossary of terms as a case study, the University College Dublin team offers the following guidelines for those seeking to develop a similar resource to support the use of inclusive language across international and cross-cultural teaching and learning contexts, including large-scale projects and consortia:

1. DEFINE SCOPE

Decide which dimensions of identity, experience, and oppression will be included (e.g., race, gender, sexuality, disability, neurodiversity), based on wider project objectives.

2. RESEARCH AND ENGAGEMENT

Base terminology on current academic research, activist guidance, and community consultation, conducting in-depth research and drawing from a variety of sources.

3. COLLABORATIVE DEVELOPMENT

Involve all project partners in drafting and reviewing entries to capture diverse perspectives. Whenever possible, engage people from the groups being referenced to offer their views or conduct sensitivity readings.

4. LIVING DOCUMENT

Maintain the resource as a “living document” that can be continually updated, allowing space for active discussion and exploration.

5. PROVIDE CONTEXT

Include definitions and examples, together with notes on regional or cultural variations. Relevant information on the history, debates, and usage of terms may also be useful.

6. REVIEW TRANSLATIONS

Ensure that translated terms are culturally and linguistically appropriate, and note differences where terminology may not fully align.

7. ACCESSIBILITY AND CLARITY

Use clear, understandable language suitable for all audiences, including non-specialists.

8. FURTHER READING

Include references and examples of further reading, such as academic literature, activist guidelines, and community input.

9. REGULAR FEEDBACK & UPDATES

Invite project members and external readers to suggest revisions or raise concerns about terminology, and schedule regular reviews to reflect evolving language, best practice, and emerging considerations.

As a process, developing an inclusive language glossary is inherently imperfect, as language is complex and context-dependent. Such a glossary should not be regarded as an infallible tool, but rather as a space for careful reflection on terminology. The decision to develop a project-specific glossary, rather than rely solely on previously established resources, reflects our view that language use should be intentional and thoughtful, addressing the challenges and nuances of expression while recognising both the power and the emancipatory potential of words.

Ultimately, the most effective approach to inclusive language is to always consider cultural context and ensure that terms used to describe people or communities are those verified and preferred by the individuals themselves. For language to truly be inclusive, it must resist essentialising, and work to reflect the complexities and specificities of individuals' and groups' experiences. For example, when discussing race, it is preferable to use specific terms whenever possible rather than homogenising categories such as "POC" (People of Colour), which can reinforce a racialised binary of "white" and "non-white" (7).

NOTES AND REFERENCES

1. Pluta, A., Mazurek, J., Wojciechowski, J., Wolak, T., Soral, W., and Bilewicz, M., 2023. "Exposure to Hate Speech Deteriorates Neurocognitive Mechanisms of the Ability to Understand Others' Pain." *Scientific Reports*, 13(4127). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31146-1>.
2. Tavits, M. and Pérez, E.O., 2019. "Language Influences Mass Opinion Toward Gender and LGBT Equality." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 116(34), pp. 16781–16786. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1908156116>.
3. hooks, b., 1989. "Choosing the Margin as a Space of Radical Openness." *Framework: The Journal of Cinema and Media*, 36, pp. 15–23. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44111660>.
4. For resources and teaching tools on the relationship between language, colonialism, and power, see SAPIENS, 2021. "Language and Colonialism," *Teaching Linguistic Anthropology: Unit 4*. Available at: <https://www.sapiens.org/teaching-unit/language-and-colonialism/>.
5. For critical disability perspectives on person-first and identity-first approaches to language, see Ferrigon, P., 2019. "Person-First Language vs. Identity-First Language: An Examination of the Gains and Drawbacks of Disability Language in Society." *Journal of Teaching Disability Studies*. Available at: <https://jtds.commons.gc.cuny.edu/person-first-language-vs-identity-first-language-an-examination-of-the-gains-and-drawbacks-of-disability-language-in-society/>.
6. American Psychological Association, 2023. *Inclusive Language Guide*. 2nd ed. Available at: <https://www.apa.org/about/apa/equity-diversity-inclusion/language-guidelines.pdf>.
7. For information on the debate around using terms like POC, listen to Gillespie, P., 2020. "Is It Time to Say 'R.I.P.' to P.O.C.?" *NPR*, 29 September. Available at: <https://www.npr.org/2020/09/29/918418825/is-it-time-to-say-r-i-p-to-p-o-c/>.

GLOSSARY OF CONCEPTS AND TERMS

A CASE STUDY OF INCLUSIVE PRACTICE IN ACTION

This glossary of terms, relating to gender, sexuality, disability, neurodiversity, race, and ethnicity, is not intended to serve as a definitive list of inclusive terminology, as many of these terms may be challenged, refined, or replaced in the coming years. Moreover, given the context-dependent nature of language, consensus is unlikely to be achieved among the communities it represents. Therefore, we present this (imperfect and in-progress) glossary of terms as an example of sustainable, inclusive practices in action, and as an invitation for ongoing dialogue on transforming language, translation, and pedagogy toward social justice.

Swans and cygnets Belfield lake, UCD © University College Dublin/Vincent Hoban

What follows is a snapshot of a “living document” that will continue to evolve and expand over time, ensuring it remains relevant and comprehensive. Definitions are collaboratively developed through the review of diverse scholarly and community-based sources, and also draw on team members’ expertise and personal experiences related to gender, sexuality, disability, race, and other aspects of identity.

For further information on specific terms or themes, please refer to the “References for Further Reading” section at the end of the document.

1. GENERAL TERMS

Accessibility: The design and delivery of environments, services, information, and activities that enable everyone – regardless of physical, sensory, cognitive, or other abilities – to participate in everyday life fully and independently. Accessibility involves identifying and removing barriers that may prevent individuals from accessing spaces, resources, or opportunities. Accessibility goes beyond physical access and includes digital, communication, and attitudinal access, ensuring that systems are inclusive by design rather than requiring adaptation or special treatment.

Active Learning: Active learning involves students engaging directly in the learning process through collaborative and participatory activities, such as discussion, problem-solving, and creation, rather than passively receiving information. Through active learning, students take part in meaningful tasks that encourage them to construct knowledge, think critically and deeply about key concepts, and apply new ideas and practices in authentic contexts. This approach supports deeper understanding and improves long-term retention of learning.

Ally: A person, group or institution that actively supports and advocates for the rights and inclusion of people from marginalised groups, without being a member of those groups themselves. Allyship is not a fixed identity but an ongoing process of action, reflection, and accountability in solidarity with others.

Barriers: Factors within a person’s environment that, either through their presence or absence, restrict functioning and limit participation in society. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasises that barriers are not only physical obstacles, but can also include inaccessible infrastructure, the absence of relevant assistive technologies, negative attitudes or stigma towards people with disabilities, and the lack of inclusive services, systems, or policies. These environmental factors can contribute to the experience of disability by preventing individuals from fully engaging in everyday life, learning, work, and community participation.

Belonging: An experience of security, support, and connection that arises when individuals feel accepted, included, and valued for who they are. It involves being recognised and respected for one’s identity, experiences, and contributions, and promotes a sense of community, engagement, and well-being.

Coalition: An alliance or group formed by different parties, factions, or organisations to achieve a specific, shared goal. Coalitions are often built around political advocacy, social change, or collective action, bringing together diverse perspectives, resources, and expertise. Activists such as Emma Dabiri (*What White People Can Do Next*, 2021) have proposed this

term as a more active and accountable alternative to “allyship,” emphasising solidarity and shared responsibility rather than one-sided support or charity.

Culturally-Responsive Teaching (sometimes called culturally relevant teaching): An educational approach that recognises the importance of incorporating students’ cultural references, identities, and lived experiences into the learning process. It draws on students’ diverse backgrounds, customs, languages, and perspectives as strengths, using them as assets to support and deepen learning. By valuing and affirming students’ identities, this approach makes teaching more relevant, engaging, and effective, particularly for learners from historically marginalised communities.

Culture: The shared beliefs, values, customs, traditions, languages, practices, and ways of life of a particular society, group of people, location, or time period. It influences identity, behaviour, and social interaction.

Decoloniality: A school of thought and practice that challenges Eurocentric knowledge, hierarchies, and ways of being in the world. It aims to de-centre the production of knowledge and recognises both colonial pasts and colonial existence between nations and within countries. Decoloniality calls for new approaches to education, politics, and society that are grounded in plurality, relationality, and justice.

Discrimination: Unfair, unequal, or prejudicial treatment of individuals or groups based on characteristics such as race, gender, age, disability, sexual orientation, religion, income status, or other aspects of identity. This treatment can be direct –such as excluding someone from a service – or indirect, where policies or practices disadvantage certain groups even if not intentionally. Discrimination can occur at individual, institutional, or structural levels, and often reinforces social inequalities and exclusion.

Diversity: The presence of individuals with a wide range of identities, backgrounds, and characteristics, such as race, culture, ethnicity, gender, sexuality, ability, and lived experience, within a learning institution or other organisation.

Empathy: The ability to understand and imagine what it might feel like to be in someone else’s situation, especially when their experiences of the world differ from your own. It involves demonstrating sensitivity, compassion, and respect by considering and responding thoughtfully to the thoughts, feelings, and experiences of others, as if you were sharing their perspective.

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI): A framework of principles and practices aimed at creating fair, respectful, and inclusive environments for all. *Equality* means ensuring that individuals and groups are not treated less favourably due to characteristics such as gender, race, disability, sexual orientation, age, or socio-economic status. *Diversity* recognises and values the differences between people, including visible and invisible characteristics, lived experiences, and perspectives. *Inclusion* refers to an effort to create environments where all individuals feel welcomed, respected, supported, and able to fully participate. Together, EDI promotes equity, belonging, and systemic

change by addressing both visible and structural forms of inequality. In different contexts, this framework may also be referred to as *DEI* (U.S.), *D&I*, *JEDI*, *DEIB*, or *IDEA*.

Equity: A state in which everyone has access to the same opportunities. As a practice, it ensures fairness by providing individuals or groups with the resources and support they need to succeed, recognising that different people may require different kinds of assistance to achieve similar outcomes.

Implicit Bias/Unconscious Bias: Subconscious attitudes, stereotypes, or prejudice that individuals hold about others. These biases can influence how one perceives, judges, and interacts with people, particularly those from marginalised or minoritised groups. Implicit or unconscious bias is sometimes referred to as *implicit prejudice* or *implicit attitude*. The use of the term implicit or unconscious bias varies across cultural contexts and different local frameworks for understanding prejudice.

Inclusion: An active and intentional effort to create and nurture environments where all individuals are treated fairly and valued for their skills, experiences, differences and perspectives. Inclusion ensures that diversity is not only present but meaningfully engaged.

Intersectionality: A term first coined by Black civil rights advocate Kimberlé Crenshaw that refers to the interconnected and overlapping nature of social identities and systems of oppression. It describes how multiple forms of discrimination – such as racism, sexism, homophobia, classism, or ableism – interact and overlap, creating unique and complex experiences of disadvantage or privilege for individuals and groups. Intersectionality highlights how these overlapping factors shape both personal experiences and the functioning of institutions and social structures, revealing that oppression cannot be fully understood by considering each form of discrimination in isolation.

Marginalised Identities: Individuals or groups whose social identities are devalued, excluded, or oppressed within society. They may experience discrimination, limited opportunities, or systemic barriers that restrict their participation, recognition, or influence.

Minoritised Identities: Individuals or groups who have been socially or politically positioned as a minority, often facing symbolic and structural discrimination due to intersecting factors such as race, gender, class, sexuality, or ability. (This term emphasises the social processes that create and maintain their marginalised status, rather than their numerical size.)

Microaggression: Intentional or unintentional behaviours or verbal remarks that may invalidate or communicate hostility and negative attitudes towards members of minoritised groups, occurring at an interpersonal or “micro” level, and often contributing to the reinforcement of stereotypes and the perpetuation of inequality.

Oppression: The systemic and pervasive mistreatment or disadvantage of individuals or groups based on aspects of their identity, such as race, gender, class, sexuality, or disability. According to Iris Marion Young (1990), oppression can take five interconnected forms:

1. **Exploitation:** Unfairly using one group's labor or resources for the benefit of another.
2. **Marginalisation:** Excluding or relegating groups to the edges of society.
3. **Powerlessness:** Limiting the ability of individuals or groups to influence decisions that affect their lives.
4. **Cultural Domination:** Imposing the dominant group's culture, norms, and values while devaluing others.
5. **Violence:** Subjecting certain groups to physical or psychological harm because of their social identity.

Prejudice: A preconceived and often negative attitude of a person or group towards another group and its members. These attitudes are typically based on unsupported stereotypes or generalisations.

Privilege: An unearned and persistent advantage that individuals receive based on intersecting aspects of their identity and social positionality, including factors like race, gender, sexuality, ability, socio-economic status, age and others. These advantages are often systemic, embedded in social structures and institutions, and may not be visibly acknowledged by those who benefit from them.

Social Class: A person's socioeconomic identity or status, which can change over time depending on life experiences, cultural context, and societal perceptions. It is a hierarchical categorisation of people in a society based on economic factors such as wealth, income, occupation, and education, often divided into upper, middle, and working classes. Social class influences opportunities, experiences, and access to resources, reflecting and reinforcing patterns of inequality.

Solidarity: The sense of unity, agreement, and mutual support within a group, grounded in shared goals, values, or interests. It involves recognising common struggles and working collectively to address inequalities, injustices, or challenges. Solidarity emphasises that the experiences and efforts of individuals are connected to the well-being of the wider community.

Stereotype: A fixed, oversimplified, and often inaccurate belief or image about a particular group of people, based on assumptions that all members share the same characteristics (for example, assuming that all women are naturally nurturing or that all men are unemotional). Stereotypes ignore individual differences and can reinforce prejudice.

Symbolic Violence: A form of non-physical violence that occurs when the norms, values, or behaviours of a dominant group are imposed on a subordinated group. Unlike physical violence, symbolic violence operates subtly through social structures, language, and cultural practices. It often manifests across social domains such as gender, sexual orientation, race, or

ethnicity, where the dominant group's values are accepted as "natural", inevitable, and the norm. This internalisation is facilitated through socialisation, where people learn and absorb the dominant group's norms and values from an early age, gradually accepting their place within this oppressive system.

Tokenism: The practice of making a superficial or symbolic effort to include members of minoritised or marginalised groups, often to create the appearance of diversity or inclusivity within a workplace, educational setting, or an organisation. Rather than making meaningful or structural changes, tokenism involves offering minimal representation or participation to those from underrepresented groups, often in ways that fail to address deeper issues of inequality. This practice is frequently used to gain social capital or improve a public image, without bringing about substantial change.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL): A framework that aims to provide all individuals with equal opportunities to learn by creating more flexible teaching and support methods, assessment, and service provision. It is based on two key principles: 1) Universal design: the process of creating environments, products, or systems (such as workplaces or classrooms) that can be used by the widest possible range of people, regardless of their individual characteristics or abilities, and 2) Inclusive design: an approach that takes into account the differences between individuals and groups to ensure that barriers to access are avoided. This might include providing transcripts for audio content or installing tactile paving for individuals with visual or mobility impairments.

2. GENDER & SEXUALITIES

Asexuality: An umbrella term for a sexual orientation characterised by little to no sexual attraction or interest in sexual activity with others. Asexuality exists on a spectrum, and individuals may identify in various ways within the ace community, such as *demisexual*, *grey-asexual*, or through *queerplatonic* relationships.

Bisexuality: Romantic, sexual, and/or emotional attraction and/or behaviour toward more than one gender. Attraction to different genders is not necessarily experienced at the same time or to the same degree. Bisexuality is a diverse umbrella that encompasses many experiences and may include identities such as *pansexual* or *fluid*.

Coming Out: The process of recognising, accepting, and disclosing one's LGBTQIA+ gender or sexuality to oneself and others. There is no single way to come out; experiences are deeply personal and can range from liberating and exciting to challenging and dangerous. While initial coming-out experiences are often significant, coming out is an ongoing, lifelong process in which individuals navigate social and cultural factors and decide how, when, and if to disclose their identities.

Cisgender/Cis: A term used to describe a person whose gender identity aligns with the sex they were assigned at birth. For example, a person who is registered as female at birth and identifies as a woman can be considered cisgender.

Cisnormativity: The assumption that all people are cisgender, e.g., that their gender identity aligns with the sex they were assigned at birth. Cisnormativity frames being cisgender as the default gendered experience, excluding the existence of transgender, nonbinary, and gender-diverse individuals. Cisnormativity can shape language, policies, and everyday interactions in ways that marginalise or erase those whose gender identity does not conform to this norm.

Cross-dresser: A person who wears clothing traditionally associated with a different gender. This does not necessarily reflect their gender identity or sexual orientation. Cross-dressing can be a form of self-expression, performance, comfort, or community involvement. While some people still use and reclaim the term cross-dresser for themselves, others prefer different language or no label at all. It is always best to use the term a person chooses for themselves without making assumptions about identity, gender, or sexuality.

Drag queen/drag king: A performer who uses exaggerated gender expression, often through clothing, makeup, and performance, to entertain, express identity, or make social commentary. Drag queens typically perform femininity, and drag kings typically perform masculinity. Drag is a form of performance

and art and does not determine a person's gender or sexuality.

Gender: A social and cultural concept that refers to roles, behaviours, expressions, and identities typically associated with being male, female, or another gender. Individuals are often socialised as a particular gender based on the assumption that their gender corresponds with the sex they are assigned at birth; however, gender may or may not align with assigned sex. As Shon Faye explains, “[w]hat it means to be a woman or a man (or neither) is not a fixed and stable entity, but a complex constellation of biological, political, economic and cultural factors, which may shift over time” (*The Transgender Issue*, 2022, p. 239).

Gender Expression: External ways in which an individual communicates or presents a gender identity, including clothing, haircut, body language, name, or pronouns.

Gender Identity: An internal sense of one's own gender, which may or may not align with the sex assigned at birth. Like gender itself, gender identity is socially constructed and shaped by historical, cultural, political, and geographical contexts. It is expressed and embodied through behaviours, appearances, and roles within society.

Genderqueer: Similar to *nonbinary*, the term is used by some people who do not identify as strictly male or female. It often reflects a rejection of the gender binary.

Gender Non-Conforming: A term used to describe people whose gender expression falls outside of the conventional expectations of masculinity or femininity. Both cisgender and transgender people can have gender expressions which are gender non-conforming.

Heteronormativity: The assumption that heterosexuality is the default, normal, or privileged form of sexual attraction, shaping institutional practices, cultural norms, and social expectations. It positions heterosexual relationships as the ideal or “natural” standard, while marginalising other sexual orientations such as homosexuality, bisexuality, or asexuality.

Homophobia: A fear, hatred, discomfort, or distrust directed towards people who are lesbian, gay, or bisexual. It can manifest individually (verbal abuse, discrimination, social exclusion, or violence) and institutionally (laws, policies, or cultural practices that disadvantage LGB people). Homophobia is often rooted in stereotypes, misinformation, or cultural and religious beliefs portraying same-sex relationships or identities as inferior or unacceptable, and contributes to the marginalisation and mistreatment of LGB individuals.

LGBTQIA+: An acronym that stands for *Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer (or questioning), Intersex, and Asexual, Aromantic, or Agender* people. The plus sign is used to denote further diverse experiences of gender and sexuality, including them under this umbrella term.

Interphobia/Intersexphobia: Fear, dislike or strong prejudice against intersex people. This prejudice can be expressed through social exclusion, stigma, discrimination, and violence. It is also evident in medical practices that pathologise intersex traits, including non-consensual surgeries or treatments aimed at “normalising” intersex bodies, often without the individual’s informed consent.

Intersex: An umbrella term that describes individuals born with physical sex characteristics that do not fit typical, binary definitions of male or female bodies (e.g., variations in chromosomal combinations or reproductive anatomy).

Nonbinary: A term for people whose gender identity does not fit exclusively within the traditional binary categories of man or woman. Nonbinary people may use a variety of pronouns, such as they/them, she/her, he/him, or neopronouns. Nonbinary identities are diverse, may shift over time, and may include terms such as *agender*, *bigender*, or *genderfluid*.

Pronouns: Words used to refer to a person in place of their name, such as *he*, *she*, *they*, *ze*. Pronouns reflect a person’s gender identity and are an important part of respectful communication. For more information on why pronouns are important, click [HERE](#).

Queer: An umbrella term used by some people to describe sexual orientations, gender identities, and expressions that do not conform to dominant norms of heterosexuality and/or cisgender identity. Once widely used as a slur, particularly against LGBTQI+ individuals, the term has since been reclaimed as a symbol of pride, resistance, and inclusivity. However, because of its history, not everyone feels comfortable with the term – so it is always important to ask and respect how someone chooses to identify. This term is highly contested in some cultures due to its history and may not translate cross-culturally. *Queer* is also used as a way to challenge rigid categories of identity, offering an alternative to binary or fixed labels. In this sense, it often carries a political or theoretical critique of heteronormativity and traditional gender roles.

Sex Registered/Assigned at Birth: The designation of a person’s sex as male, female, or intersex at the time of their birth. This designation is typically based on physical characteristics such as anatomy or chromosomes, and is often recorded on official documents that can influence societal expectations and assumptions about gender. However, it may not necessarily align with an individual’s experience of gender.

Sexual Orientation/Sexuality: A person’s emotional, romantic, or sexual attraction to other people, distinguished by categories such as *heterosexual*, *homosexual*, *bisexual*, *asexual*, *pansexual*, and others.

Trans: A term for people whose gender identity or expression differs from the sex they were assigned at birth. Trans is often used as an umbrella term encompassing a range of identities and experiences that challenge traditional expectations of gender. This may include *transgender*, *transsexual*, and *trans* men and women, as well as *nonbinary*, *genderqueer*, and other gender-

diverse identities. Pronouns used by trans people vary, including *he/him*, *she/her*, *they/them*, or others.

Trans Man: A person who was assigned female at birth and identifies and/or expresses themselves as a man. Gender identity and expression are personal and complex, and not all trans men experience or express their identity in the same way. For instance, while many trans men use *he/him* pronouns, this varies.

Trans Woman: A person who was assigned male at birth and identifies and/or expresses themselves as a woman. Gender identity and expression are personal and complex, and not all trans women experience or express their identity in the same way. For instance, while many trans women use *she/her* pronouns, this varies.

Transition: A process undertaken by a trans person to bring their gender expression and/or body into alignment with their gender identity. This can be a complex process occurring over a long period, and the actions taken will vary depending on the individual. Transition can include:

- **Social Transition:** Changes in how a person expresses their gender, such as adopting a different name or pronouns, altering clothing or appearance, and informing family, friends, and/or co-workers about transitioning. Not all transgender people choose to undergo social transition, or may choose to do so only in certain contexts.
- **Legal Transition:** A legal transition, involving updating official documents, such as passports, driver's licences, or bank accounts, to reflect a new name or gender marker. Not all transgender people choose to undergo legal transition.
- **Medical Transition:** This may involve hormone replacement therapy (HRT) and/or surgical procedures. Not all transgender people choose to undergo medical transition.

Transphobia: A dislike, fear, or strong prejudice against transgender people, which can manifest individually, institutionally, and systemically. Transphobia contributes to the marginalisation and mistreatment of transgender individuals, affecting their rights, safety, and wellbeing. Individual forms include verbal abuse, misgendering, refusal to use correct pronouns, physical or sexual assault, and discrimination in workplaces or housing. Institutional transphobia can appear as barriers to gender-affirming healthcare, restrictions on bathroom access, legal obstacles in changing name or gender markers, or, in some countries, requirements such as sterilisation for legal recognition of gender. Systemic transphobia is evident in underrepresentation or negative portrayal in media and education, policies and practices that reinforce gender norms, and unequal access to social services or protections.

3. DISABILITY & NEURODIVERSITY

Ableism: Societal beliefs or practices based upon the assumption that being able-bodied is the norm and that any physical, cognitive, or developmental difference should be fixed, cured, or altered. Occurring on individual, institutional, and systemic levels, ableism leads to the marginalisation, discrimination, or devaluation of people with disabilities. Examples include derogatory language or stereotyping (*individual*), lack of workplace accommodations or inaccessible public transport (*institutional*), and broader cultural narratives that equate disability with deficiency or reduced value (*systemic*).

Ability: A person's experience in relation to their capacity to perform tasks, actions, or activities (physical, cognitive, emotional, or social). Abilities vary widely between individuals and can be shaped by a range of factors, including health, environment, access to support, and societal attitudes.

Accessible Technology: Specialised tools, devices, and systems designed with the needs of a broad range of individuals – including those with disabilities – in mind. This often includes built-in customisation features allowing users to individualise the experience to suit their needs.

Adaptive Technologies: Specialised tools, devices, or systems designed to support individuals who cannot use standardised versions of tools or devices. Adaptive technologies are often tailored to meet specific needs related to vision, hearing, mobility, learning, or communication, enabling greater access and participation in everyday activities. Examples include frequency modulation (FM) systems, reading guides, and audio players or recorders.

Ally (tool): An accessibility tool for virtual learning environments (e.g., Blackboard or Brightspace). It helps improve the usability and accessibility of course content by automatically generating alternative, accessible formats for students. Ally also provides educators with feedback and guidance on how to make their course materials more inclusive and accessible.

Assistive Technologies: Specialised tools, devices, or systems designed to support individuals with disabilities by enhancing their ability to perform functions that might otherwise be difficult or impossible. Examples include mobility aids such as crutches or wheelchairs, hearing aids, screen readers, and descriptive video services.

Compulsory Able-bodiedness: A term coined by theorist Robert McRuer that describes the cultural assumption that able-bodiedness is the standard and ideal state of being, positioning disability as imperfect or lacking. Margaret Price and other crip scholars have developed a related concept, Compulsory Able-mindedness, to describe similar assumptions about mental and cognitive norms.

Crip Theory: A strand of critical cultural analysis developed within the interdisciplinary fields of disability studies and queer theory in the 21st century. As described by Robert McRuer, crip theory seeks to resist the “contemporary spectacle of able-bodied heteronormativity” (*Crip Theory*, 2006, p. 3). Like the term *queer*, *crip* is a reclaimed and historically stigmatised term; therefore, it is important to check with individuals before using it to describe them or their identities.

Deficit-based Language: The opposite of strengths-based language. Deficit-based language focuses on perceived limitations, impairments, or “deficiencies”. It is often found in medical or clinical literature related to disability and impairment. Preferences vary culturally and, while some disabled people may prefer this language, it is always best to check individual preferences. Common examples include terms such as *diagnosis*, *condition*, *person with autism*, and *symptoms*.

Disability: A complex and evolving concept shaped by social, cultural, legal, political, and historical contexts, as well as by individual positionality and identity. While disability is often associated with illness, age, or impairment, it should not be understood as a direct consequence of these differences. Rather, disability refers to the mechanisms of exclusion and marginalisation that arise from societal norms, structures, and expectations. At the same time, many disabled people have reclaimed disability as a positive identity category and a political platform for organising and connecting with others who face exclusion based on compulsory able-bodiedness and able-mindedness.

Critical Disability Studies (CDS): An academic discipline that examines disability through a critical lens, challenging the notion of disabled people’s victimhood and questioning societal norms that privilege certain bodies, minds, and experiences as “normal” or “ideal”. Related to a social model of disability, CDS identifies social, cultural, and structural barriers as impediments to disabled people’s full and meaningful participation in society. This framework opposes a medical model, which views disability as a personal deficit or burden, and a condition to be treated or corrected. Critiquing such ableist perspectives, CDS also often examines how disability interacts with race, gender, class, sexuality, and other axes of oppression. While offering powerful critiques, CDS has sometimes been criticised as overly academic, based on theory rather than practice.

High- or Low- Functioning: A term used in reference to invisible disabilities, such as neurodivergence (specifically autism). Used to describe different “levels” of an individual’s neurodivergence, including intellectual or communication capabilities, and thus the ability to participate in society. Some advocates disapprove of the term as it fails to capture the broadness and complexity of disability.

Identity-first Language: A term that describes how some individuals with disabilities prefer to refer to themselves. Those who see their disability as an important part of their self-identity may prefer to use language that refers to their disability, e.g., *a blind person*. It is recommended that one only refers to someone this way if one is aware of their preference. Otherwise, it is

recommended that one use person-first language, e.g., *a person who is blind*.

Inspiration Porn: A term coined by Stella Young, inspiration porn means to think of disabled people's everyday lives as consecutive moments of struggle that inspire non-disabled people to regard their own lives as less of a struggle for their own gratification. It risks the perpetuation of harmful stereotypes of disabled lives as unliveable and unrelatable. For more information, listen to Stella Young speak about this [HERE](#).

Invisible Disability: A disability that is not immediately apparent, also referred to as a *hidden disability*. Examples include mental health conditions, vision or hearing impairments, sensory or processing difficulties.

Medical Model: A way of understanding disability that focuses on "scientific" or "objective" facts, framing both illness and some typical human variations as abnormal. This model has been critiqued by disability activists, advocates, and scholars for assigning deficiency solely to the individual, rather than acknowledging the impact of social inclusion/exclusion. In response, some medical model users have adopted more inclusive language, particularly as identity-first and person-first language models have been popularised.

Neurodiversity: A term that refers to the natural variation in the ways that people think, learn, and process information and the world around them. All humans are neurodiverse, meaning each person has a particular neurotype, such as *neurotypical* or *neurodivergent*.

Neurodivergent: Ways of thinking and processing information that diverge from what a particular society considers "normal" or "typical". Neurodivergence is often associated with autism, ADHD, OCD, dyslexia, or other conditions. It can be developmental or acquired (e.g., through injury), and may emerge in childhood or adulthood. It is also shaped by intersecting systems of discrimination, such as racism, sexism, and gender or heteronormative stereotypes.

Neurotypical: A way of thinking and processing information that reflects the normative idea of "sameness" in intellectual and experiential processing, and of homogeneity of a social group. The term is commonly used in contrast to **neurodivergent**. Assumptions of neurotypicality often underpin ableist attitudes and systems, particularly when the experiences and needs of neurodivergent individuals are marginalised or overlooked.

Non-Verbal: Individuals who do not speak are sometimes referred to as non-verbal, although they may understand language and communicate in alternative ways, such as Sign Language. It is therefore more accurate and respectful to use the phrase "non-speaking".

Operable: One of the four main principles of digital accessibility. An interface is operable when users can navigate and interact with it without requiring actions they are unable to perform. This includes support for keyboard navigation, sufficient time to read or complete tasks, and avoiding content that could trigger seizures.

Perceivable: One of the four main principles of digital accessibility. Information and user interface components are perceivable if they are presented in ways that users can perceive, regardless of their sensory abilities. This includes alternatives for visual or auditory content, such as text alternatives and captions.

PwD: An acronym which stands for Person/People with Disabilities.

Robust: One of the four main principles of digital accessibility. Digital content is robust when it is compatible with a wide range of browsers, devices, and assistive technologies, both current and future. This ensures content remains accessible as technologies evolve.

Sanism: Discrimination or oppression against people perceived to have a mental disorder.

Screen Reader: A form of assistive technology often used by people with visual impairments. It converts text, buttons, images, and other screen elements into speech or braille.

Social Model: A way of understanding disability that focuses on how people are positioned and exist within society, particularly examining how disabling experiences are created by social barriers, rather than an individual's physical, cognitive, or developmental differences. In recent years, this model has been criticised for ignoring the impact of chronic illness and pain that are not solely the result of social barriers. Some social model users now include recognition of the impact of physical differences alongside social factors.

Strengths-based Language: The opposite of deficit-based language. Strengths-based language focuses on individuals' abilities, identities, and contributions, rather than perceived limitations or deficits. It is often used by disability activists and advocates. Some disabled people may prefer this language, but it is best to check with them before using it. Examples of such language include, *autistic person*, *autism assessment*, and *characteristics*.

Text Alternative/Alt Text: A short text description that is programmatically associated with non-text content, such as charts, images, or icons, enabling screen readers to convey the content to users who are blind or have low vision.

Understandable: One of the four main principles of digital accessibility. Content is understandable when it is presented in clear, consistent, and predictable ways that are easy to read and use, ensuring it can be grasped by the widest possible audience.

Universal Design: A concept that refers to designing environments, products, services, and systems so they can be used by the widest possible range of people without the need for adaptation or specialised design. The goal is to ensure that people with different abilities, bodies, sensory needs, and cognitive styles can access and use things equally and independently. This emerged from disability rights and inclusive design movements, particularly through the work of Ronald Mace, who argued that accessibility should not be an

afterthought or a separate accommodation. Instead, design should anticipate diversity in human ability from the outset. Rather than creating a “standard” user and then adding adaptations for those who do not fit that norm, universal design builds flexibility and accessibility into the original design so that as many people as possible can use the same space or system.

Usability: A term which refers to how easily, effectively, and efficiently a person, including disabled people, can use a product or a system, and how satisfied they are with the experience.

WCAG: The Web Content Accessibility Guidelines. These guidelines are developed by the Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), the main international standards organisation for the Internet. WCAGs provide a series of recommendations aimed at making online content more accessible to people with disabilities. The guidelines are based on four key principles, stating that digital content must be “*POUR:*” *Perceivable, Operable, Understandable, and Robust.*

4. RACE & ETHNICITY

Affirmative Action: A set of governmental or institutional policies designed to address systemic discrimination and historical inequalities. Affirmative action aims to increase the representation and participation of underrepresented groups – such as minoritised racial, ethnic, gender, or sexual communities – in areas like employment, education, or public service. These policies may include targeted recruitment, support programmes, or preferential consideration in selection processes.

Antiracism: A concept and practice that refers to the active identification and opposition of racism in all forms, including individual, institutional, and systemic racism. It upholds a system of equity and justice across these spheres to create fair outcomes for people across racial and ethnic groups.

BIPoC: An acronym which stands for Black, Indigenous (and) People of Colour. This term is specific to Anglo-American contexts and other countries may have different classifications for race/ethnicity (e.g., *BAME* in the UK). The use of such umbrella terms is debated, as it can risk homogenising individuals' diverse experiences of racialisation and reinforcing a false binary of "white" versus "non-white". Wherever possible, it is preferable to use more specific terminology when referencing the racial and ethnic experiences of particular people or communities.

Codeswitching: The practice of shifting between different speech styles, dialects, or languages depending on social context. Individuals may alter how they speak in order to align with the expectations of a particular audience or setting, such as a classroom, workplace, or social group. This is often connected to issues of race, ethnicity, and cultural identity, as individuals from minoritised groups may feel pressure to conform to dominant linguistic norms to avoid discrimination or negative stereotypes. For example, someone might suppress an accent that is commonly stigmatised or use an alternate name to reduce the likelihood of mispronunciation or bias.

Colourism: The practice of discriminating against darker skin whilst favouring lighter skin. It is linked to racism, unconscious biases, and "white" beauty standards, and can operate both within and across racial and ethnic groups. Colourism exists in many societies but manifests differently (e.g., South Asia, Africa, Latin America), and the terminology may vary.

Critical Race Theory (CRT): An interdisciplinary field of study that examines the relationship between social conceptions of race, ethnicity, law, and media. CRT perceives racism as a systemic issue rather than a result of individual bias or prejudice. It came into being following the Civil rights movement in the United States in the 1960s.

Cultural Appropriation: The unacknowledged or inappropriate adoption of cultural elements (e.g., symbols, art, language, customs) of one culture by members of another – often more dominant – culture. Cultural appropriation frequently involves commodification, where aspects of a culture are taken out of context and used for profit or aesthetic value, sometimes against the explicit wishes of the originating community. It is particularly harmful when it reinforces existing cultural power imbalances or erases the cultural significance of the appropriated elements.

Cultural Reclamation: The process by which individuals or communities recover and reassert cultural practices, symbols, languages, or identities that have been suppressed, erased, or appropriated due to colonisation, oppression, or forced assimilation. Cultural reclamation serves as a powerful act of resistance and self-determination for minorities and oppressed groups, enabling them to reconnect with their heritage and challenge dominant narratives.

Decolonisation: The process of “undoing” colonialism by challenging and dismantling colonial systems of power, and embracing Indigenous knowledge and methods of governance.

Ethnicity: The socially constructed categorisation of people based on shared cultural traits such as language, religion, ancestry, and traditions. It can involve a sense of common history, heritage, or group belonging. Ethnicity may be identified through both self-identification and recognition by others. Unlike race, which is often linked to perceived physical differences, ethnicity emphasises cultural and social factors, though it can intersect with other forms of social hierarchy and power.

Ethnocentrism: The act of judging another culture by the values and standards of one's own culture. This can lead to misrepresentations and unfair judgments of the behaviours or beliefs of other cultures.

Eurocentrism: The view of Europe/the West as the centre of world events and superior to all other cultures. This attitude often includes the universalisation of European cultural standards, and positioning European people and cultures as the benchmark of humanity, culture, knowledge, aesthetics, and ethics.

Global Majority: A term for the world's non-white populations (Black, Asian, Indigenous, mixed-heritage, etc.), who collectively make up the majority (85%) of the Earth's people, challenging Eurocentric views that label them as "minorities". This term was coined by Black British educator and activist Rosemary Campbell-Stephens MBE. Read her definition [HERE](#).

Indigeneity: A state of being Indigenous (also known as “Indigenoussness”). It encompasses the identity and knowledge that is coined, produced, and narrated by the Indigenous peoples themselves.

Minoritised: A term used to describe social groups – most often racial or ethnic – that are rendered smaller or less powerful within a society due to systemic social, political, or economic processes. Using this term instead of *minority*

emphasises how structural and social forces actively marginalise these groups through power and domination, rather than framing them solely in relation to a numerical majority.

Minority: A term sometimes used to describe a social group - most often racial or ethnic - that is smaller in number compared to the majority population within a society. The broad use of this term has been problematised, and some scholars and activists prefer describing such groups as "historically minoritised" or *minoritised* to emphasise how ethnic or social groups are rendered smaller or less powerful through systemic social, political, or economic processes. In this way, "minoritised" highlights the active, ongoing processes of discrimination and exclusion that reduce a group's power, rather than framing them solely in numerical terms.

Mixed (race, heritage, etc.): an identity term for individuals who have parents or ancestors from more than one racial or ethnic background. This identity can reflect a combination of cultures, histories, and lived experiences, and may be understood or expressed differently by each individual. Terms used by individuals to describe their own experiences of race or heritage may vary, and terms surrounding the "mixing" of race may be viewed as linked to colonial histories of eugenics (read more [HERE](#)).

POC: An acronym meaning Person/People of Colour. The term is inclusive of a wide range of racial and ethnic groups, including Asian, Aboriginal, Black, Latinx, and others who are not considered white in a given context. Like *BIPoC*, the use of this umbrella term is debated, as it can obscure important differences between communities. Whenever possible, more specific terminology is preferable when discussing racial identities, experiences, or issues.

Race: The socially constructed categorisation of people based on assumed shared physical traits, such as skin colour, that are given social and political meaning and positioned within a hierarchical system. These categories are not biologically grounded, but have historically been used to justify systems of power, privilege, and inequality.

Racial Profiling: A form of discriminatory criminal or social profiling involving the selective targeting of individuals from historically minorised groups based on race, ethnicity, religion, or country of origin, rather than on actual behaviour or concrete evidence. This practice can result in unjust surveillance, arrests, or violence, and reinforces broader patterns of systemic racism and social inequality. Racial profiling is not limited to policing or the criminal justice system; it can also occur in contexts such as education, where teachers or administrators may disproportionately discipline or monitor students based on race or ethnicity.

Racialisation: A sociological concept that is often used to describe the processes of ascribing racial meanings to individuals or groups to construct identities and social hierarchies. There are varying definitions and uses of this term in academic scholarship and the process and understanding of racialisation differ cross-culturally, especially where colonial histories are distinct.

Racism: The system of power, operating at individual, institutional, and structural levels, through which a social and political hierarchy is constructed based on perceived racial differences. Racism manifests in behaviours, practices, and policies that racialise, discriminate against, marginalise, or oppress people. Racism is sometimes categorised into four specific forms: *interpersonal racism*; *institutional racism*; *structural racism*; and *internalised racism*, as shown [HERE](#).

Segregation: The social, spatial, and symbolic separation of groups of people based on their race, ethnicity, income, or age.

White Privilege: The unearned and often unquestioned advantages, entitlements and benefits associated with identifying or appearing as a white person in a culture that operates on privileging and defaulting “whiteness”. This form of privilege may include internal and external manifestations at the individual, interpersonal, cultural, or institutional levels. White privilege can also be utilised by white allies to challenge racist oppression.

White Supremacy: The ideology and system of power and domination in which whiteness is positioned as the social, cultural, and political norm, granting white people disproportionate privilege and authority. White supremacy operates through overt racism, as well as through cultural narratives, institutions, and everyday practices that reinforce racial hierarchies and maintain the centrality of whiteness in society.

White Saviourism: When a white person positions themselves as a rescuer for people from historically minoritised racial groups, often driven by a self-serving or unconscious belief that white people have the responsibility to save or protect these communities. This mindset assumes these communities lack the knowledge or ability to help themselves and is rooted in colonial and racial superiority, reinforcing racial hierarchies and centring white “heroes.”

REFERENCES FOR FURTHER READING

Adams, R., Reiss, B., and Serlin, D., eds., 2015. *Keywords for Disability Studies*. New York: NYU Press.

Aggleton, P., Cover, R., Logie, C.H., Newman, C.E. and Parker, R., eds. 2024. *Routledge Handbook of Sexuality, Gender, Health and Rights*. 2nd ed. New York: Routledge.

Ahmed, S., 2017. *Living a Feminist Life*. 1st ed. Durham: Duke University Press.

Alim, H.S., Rickford, J.R. and Ball, A.F., 2016. *Raciolinguistics: How Language Shapes Our Ideas About Race*. New York: Oxford University Press.

Angouri, J. and Baxter, J., eds., 2021. *The Routledge Handbook of Language, Gender, and Sexuality*. London: Routledge.

Annamma, S. A., Connor, D. and Ferri, B., 2012. "Dis/ability Critical Race Studies (DisCrit): Theorizing at the Intersections of Race and Dis/Ability." *Race Ethnicity and Education*, 16(1), pp. 1–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1lg9616>.

American Psychological Association, 2023. *Inclusive Language Guide*. 2nd ed. Available at: <https://www.apa.org/about/apa/equity-diversity-inclusion/language-guidelines.pdf> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

Batsleer, J., Burman, E., Chantler, K., McIntosh, H., Pantling, K., Smailes, S. and Warner, S., 2002. *Domestic Violence and Minoritisation: Supporting Women to Independence*. Manchester: Manchester Metropolitan University.

Battiste, M., 2013. *Decolonizing Education: Nourishing the Learning Spirit*. Saskatoon: Purich Press.

BelongTo LGBTQ+ Youth Ireland, 2024. "LGBTQ+ Language." Available at: <https://www.belongto.org/support-for-someone-else/at-home/lgbtq-language> [Accessed 11 Apr. 2024].

Bonilla-Silva, E., 1997. "Rethinking Racism: Toward a Structural Interpretation." *American Sociological Review*, 62(3), pp. 465–480. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2657316>.

Bourdieu, P., 1991. *Language and Symbolic Power*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.

Bourdieu, P., 2001. *Masculine Domination*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.

Brown, L.X.Z., 2014. *All the Weight of Our Dreams: On Living Racialized Autism*. Washington, DC: Autistic Women & Nonbinary Network.

Butler, J., 1990. *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*. New York: Routledge.

Butler, J., 2024. *Who's Afraid of Gender?* New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux.

Caldas-Coulthard, C.R., ed., 2020. *Innovations and Challenges: Women, Language and Sexism*. London: Routledge.

Campbell-Stephens, R.M., 2020. "Global Majority; Decolonising the Language and Reframing the Conversation about Race." Leeds Beckett University. Available at: <https://www.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/-/media/files/schools/school-of-education/final-leeds-beckett-1102-global-majority.pdf> [Accessed 20 Aug. 2025].

Cameron, D., 2024. *Language, Sexism and Misogyny*. New York: Routledge.

Centre for Excellence in Universal Design, 2024. "The 7 Principles of Universal Design." Available at: <https://universaldesign.ie/about-universal-design/the-7-principles> [Accessed 20 Sept. 2025].

City of Seattle, Office for Civil Rights, 2021. "4 Types of Racism." August. Available at: <https://www.seattle.gov/documents/Departments/RSJI/Resources/RSJI-4-Types-of-Racism-August-2021-City-of-Seattle-Office-for-Civil-Rights.pdf> [Accessed 20 Aug. 2025].

Connor, D.J., Ferri, B.A., and Annamma, S.A., 2016. *DisCrit: Disability Studies and Critical Race Theory in Education*. New York: Teachers College Press.

Cordoba, S., 2023. *Non-Binary Gender Identities: The Language of Becoming*. London: Routledge.

Crenshaw, K., 1989. "Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics." *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 1989(1), pp. 139–167. Available at: <https://chicagounbound.uchicago.edu/uclf/vol1989/iss1/8>.

Crenshaw, K., 1991. "Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence Against Women of Color." *Stanford Law Review*, 43(6), pp. 1241–1299. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1229039>.

Dabiri, E., 2021. *What White People Can Do Next: From Allyship to Coalition*. London: Penguin Books.

Davis, A.Y., 1994. *Women, Race and Class*. London: Women's Press.

Delgado, R., and Stefancic, J., 2017. *Critical Race Theory: An Introduction*. New York: NYU Press.

Eckert, P. and McConnell-Ginet, S., 2013. *Language and Gender*. 2nd ed. New York: Cambridge University Press.

Eddo-Lodge, R., 2022. *Why I'm No Longer Talking to White People About Race*. Expanded ed. London: Bloomsbury Publishing.

Enable Ireland, 2024. "Glossary." Available at: <https://enableireland.ie/resources/glossary> [Accessed 10 Apr. 2024].

Equity in the Centre (EIC), 2024. "Racial Equity Tools." Available at: <https://www.racialequitytools.org/glossary> [Accessed 10 Apr. 2024].

Erevelles, N., 2011. *Disability and Difference in Global Contexts: Enabling a Transformative Body Politic*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

Faye, S., 2022. *The Transgender Issue: An Argument for Justice*. London: Penguin Books.

Foucault, M., 1978. *The History of Sexuality, Volume 1: An Introduction*. New York: Pantheon Books.

Garland-Thomson, R., 1997. *Extraordinary Bodies: Figuring Physical Disability in American Culture and Literature*. New York: Columbia University Press.

Garner, S., 2010. "Racialisation." In: *Racisms: An Introduction*, pp. 19–32. London: SAGE Publications Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446279106.n2>.

Hall, S., 1997. *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Halberstam, J. 2018. *Trans*: A Quick and Quirky Account of Gender Variability*. Oakland: University of California Press.

Hayfield, N., 2021. *Bisexual and Pansexual Identities: Exploring and Challenging Invisibility and Invalidation*. New York: Routledge.

Heller, M. and McElhinny, B.S., 2017. *Language, Capitalism, Colonialism: Toward a Critical History*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.

hooks, b., 2000. *Feminism Is for Everybody: Passionate Politics*. Cambridge: South End Press.

Jagose, A., 1997. *Queer Theory: An Introduction*. New York: NYU Press.

Kelly, N., 2022. "Why is Inspiration Porn Entrenched in Our Attitudes Towards Disability?" *Disability Rights UK*, 10 January. Available at: <https://www.disabilityrightsuk.org/news/why-inspiration-porn-entrenched-our-attitudes-towards-disability-ned-kelly/> [Accessed 20 Sept. 2025].

Kendi, I.X., 2019. *How to Be an Antiracist*. London: The Bodley Head.

Kiesling, S.F., 2019. *Language, Gender, and Sexuality: An Introduction*. London: Routledge.

Ladau, E., 2021. *Demystifying Disability: What to Know, What to Say, and How to Be an Ally*. New York: Ten Speed Press.

Ladson-Billings, G., 2021. *Critical Race Theory in Education: A Scholar's Journey*. New York: Teachers College Press.

Legal Defense Fund, 2022. *Critical Race Theory: Frequently Asked Questions*. Available at: <https://www.naacpldf.org/critical-race-theory-faq/> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

Lorde, A., 1984. *Sister Outsider: Essays and Speeches*. Berkeley: Crossing Press.

McRuer, R., 2006. *Crip Theory: Cultural Signs of Queerness and Disability*. New York: NYU Press.

McWhorter, J., 2025. *Pronoun Trouble: The Story of Us in Seven Little Words*. 1st ed. New York: Penguin Publishing Group.

Mignolo, W.D., and Walsh, C.E., 2018. *On Decoloniality: Concepts, Analytics, Praxis*. Durham: Duke University Press.

Ngũgĩ, W. T., 1986. *Decolonising the Mind: The Politics of Language in African Literature*. London: James Currey.

Ontario Human Rights Commission, 2013. "Appendix 1: Glossary of Human Rights Terms." Available at: <https://www.ohrc.on.ca/en/teaching-human-rights-ontario-guide-ontario-schools/appendix-1-glossary-human-rights-terms> [Accessed 11 Apr. 2024].

Price, M., 2024. *Crip Spacetime: Access, Failure, and Accountability in Academic Life*. Duke University Press.

Pronouns.org, n.d. "What Are Personal Pronouns and Why Do They Matter?" Available at: <https://pronouns.org/what-and-why/> [Accessed 11 Apr. 2024].

Puar, J.K., 2017. *The Right to Maim: Debility, Capacity, Disability*. London: Duke University Press.

Race Equality Action Group, n.d. *Short Guide to Understanding Race and Ethnicity Language and Terminology*. Queen Mary University of London. Available at: <https://www.qmul.ac.uk/media/black-history-month/SGLT.pdf> [Accessed 20 Sept. 2025].

Rees, E., ed., 2023. *The Routledge Companion to Gender, Sexuality and Culture*. New York: Routledge.

Samuels, E., 2014. *Fantasies of Identification: Disability, Gender, Race*. New York: NYU Press.

TEDx Talks, 2014. "Inspiration Porn and the Objectification of Disability: Stella Young at TEDxSydney 2014." YouTube, 13 May. Available at: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SxrS7-l_sMQ [Accessed 20 Sept. 2025].

The 519, 2020. "Glossary of Terms." The 519, February. Available at: <https://www.the519.org/education-training/glossary/> [Accessed 20 Sept. 2025].

Titchkosky, T., 2007. *Reading and Writing Disability Differently: The Textured Life of Embodiment*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.

TU Dublin, 2023. "Inclusive Language Guidelines: Infographic." Available at: <https://www.tudublin.ie/media/website/explore/about-the-university/strategic-plan/creating-impact/documents/TU-Dublin-Inclusive-Language-Guidelines-Infographic-FULL-Final-Oct-2023.pdf> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

Understood, n.d. "Disability Inclusion Glossary." Available at: <https://www.understood.org/en/articles/disability-inclusion-glossary> [Accessed 11 Apr. 2024].

University of Bristol, n.d. "Inclusive Writing Guide." Available at: <https://www.bristol.ac.uk/style-guides/writing/inclusive/> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

University of California, Berkeley, Haas School of Business, n.d. "Understanding Inclusive Language Playbook." Available at: <https://haas.berkeley.edu/wp-content/uploads/Understanding-IL-Playbook-3.pdf> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

University of Edinburgh, n.d. "Inclusive Language." Available at: <https://editorial-style.ed.ac.uk/editorial-style-guide/language-and-tone/inclusive-language> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

University of Groningen, 2024. "Inclusive Language Style Guide." Available at: <https://www.rug.nl/about-ug/policy-and-strategy/diversity-and-inclusion/pdf/university-of-groningen-inclusive-language-style-guide-may2024.pdf> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

University of Leeds, n.d. "Inclusive Language Guidance." Available at: <https://equality.leeds.ac.uk/support-and-resources/inclusive-language-guidance/> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

University of Richmond, n.d. "Inclusive Language Guide." Available at: <https://belonging.richmond.edu/resources/inclusive-language-guide.html> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

Walker, N, 2021. *Neuroqueer Heresies: Notes on the Neurodiversity Paradigm, Autistic Empowerment, and Postnormal Possibilities*. Fort Worth: Autonomous Press, LLC.

Walcott, R. R., 2018. "Against Social Justice and the Limits of Diversity: Or, Black People and Freedom." In: E. Tuck & K. W. Yang, eds. *Toward What Justice? Describing Diverse Dreams of Justice in Education*. New York: Routledge, pp. 85–99.

Warner, M., 1991. "Introduction: Fear of a Queer Planet." *Social Text*, 29, pp. 3–17. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/466295>.

WCAG, 2022. "WCAG Glossary." Available at: <https://wcag.com/resource/wcag-com-glossary/> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2024].

Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI), 2023. "Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.2." World Wide Web Consortium. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

Wingrove-Haugland, E., and McLeod, J., 2021. "Not 'Minority' but 'Minoritized.'" *Teaching Ethics*, 21(1), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5840/tej20221799>.

Woozeer, L., 2022. "As a 'mixed' person, the language to describe me isn't fit for purpose." *The Guardian*, 30 August. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2022/aug/30/mixed-person-language-vocabulary> [Accessed 20 Sept. 2025].

World Health Organization (WHO), 2001. *International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF)*. Geneva: World Health Organization.

World Health Organization (WHO), 2011. *World Report on Disability*. Geneva: WHO Press. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241564182> [Accessed 30 Apr. 2025].

Young, I. M., 2008. "The Five Faces of Oppression." In: G. Henderson & M. Waterstone, eds. *Geographic Thought: A Praxis Perspective*. Milton Park: Taylor & Francis, pp. 55–71.

ABOUT UNITE

UNITE: University Network for Inclusive and Digital Education is an Erasmus+ Consortium composed of European universities and organisations in Czechia, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Spain. The primary goal of UNITE is to promote inclusion, drive digital transformation, and improve teaching quality in higher education by creating innovative programs, digital tools, and strategies. By utilising the consortium's diverse expertise, it aims to establish best practices that universities can implement to reduce inequalities and encourage both innovation and inclusion.

University College Dublin (UCD) is a public research university within the National University of Ireland. As an institution, we bring expertise in equality, diversity, and inclusion, accessibility in education, and teaching and learning innovation.

Our participation in the UNITE project draws on our experience in developing inclusive teaching strategies and implementing the principles of Universal Design for Learning (UDL).

Our team also specialises in teaching and learning, transformative pedagogy, educational technology, and social justice scholarship, including work on gender, sexualities, race, migration, and cultural studies.

The UCD project team is based in the **Observatory of Masculinities**, a space for critical reflection, research, and dialogue on men and masculinities through intersectional and decolonial lenses. We aim to cultivate inclusive learning spaces where knowledge is co-created within a community of learners.

Find out more about the Observatory here: www.ucd.ie/masculinities

